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SPEECH ETIQUETTE IN ENGLISH LESSONS

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ABSTRACT

Speech etiquette often plays a decisive role in the design of the statement, in the selection of means in speech communication. A student receiving a pedagogical education must not only master the literary norm, but also carefully study the culture of the country of the language being studied, the specifics of speech etiquette, verbal etiquette formulas and clichés characteristic of the language.

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One of the important elements of culture and an integral part of the general system of etiquette behavior of a person in society is speech etiquette. The last decades are characterized by an increased interest in the problems of studying speech etiquette as one of the most important components of the communicative process. Knowledge of the features of national etiquette traditions contributes to better understanding in interethnic communication, which makes speech etiquette one of the most significant components of teaching a foreign language. In order to organize the speech interaction of students, it is not enough to present them with a speech task, samples of speech actions, such methodological techniques are needed that would provide the necessary speech interaction of schoolchildren in a foreign language. The product of oral speech is a speech statement, a speech message. Relying on awareness of patterns of communication in their native language helps children "discover" the laws of both their native language and the new, English language. The study of speech etiquette by students is an integral component of successful mastery of a foreign language.

Most of the phrases used in the classroom are situational, which allows the teacher to vary the forms of instructions within the learning process. By using phrases in specific situations, the teacher gives students a series of speech patterns: the student hears new words in context and develops the important skill of language guessing in determining the meanings of new words.

The speech of the teacher in the English lesson is mostly neutral and does not contain vocabulary typical of the scientific style. At the grammatical level, phrases such as would rather, had better, let's, etc. are used.

In orders, the question is rare - Will you stop talking?

Request - Do you mind repeating what you said? Do you want to try the next one?

Suggestion and Persuasion - Let's try the next exercise as well, shall we?if you finish this off at home?

Since interrogative sentences give more politeness to statements, we can conclude that requests are the most polite. With the help of a polite address, the speaker expects to perform this or that action, psychologically influencing the student and thereby increasing the chance of performance.

A certain amount of politeness is given to the formulas of speech etiquette by an interrogative-negative form. The quantitative data looks like this.

Order - Don't you help him, Mark? I would like you not to keep interrupting.

Suggestion and persuasion - Let's not waste any more time. Why don't we act this conversation out?

The use of negative-interrogative sentences in etiquette formulas reduces their categorical nature. Statements become more polite, which helps to maintain contact between the interlocutors.

Also, I would like to pay special attention to the use of modal verbs.

Order - You must have this finished by Monday. You are not to talk. Request - Can you say that again? Could you share with Anne today?

Suggestion and Persuasion - You may sit down again now. We might just as well stop here this time.

Modal verbs are used to make the statement more polite and to maintain a benevolent relationship between the speaker and the listener.

Order	Request	Suggestion and persuasion
I would like you to do this. Let the window down.	Would you like to do this, please? I wish you'd be quiet.	Let's do this, (shall we?). Let's not do this. Don't let's do this.
I (would) prefer you to do this.	Will you do this, please?	What if / suppose we do (did) this?
I want / expect/ insist you to do this.	Would / do you mind doing this?	How about doing this?
I would rather you didn't do that.	Would you mind if I do this?	I suggest / suppose you (will) do this
I do insist you to do this.	Would you be so kind (enough) as to do this?	It would be a good idea to do this.

Also, the most common grammatical construction in the teacher's stimulus replicas is the imperative mood. The command Open the window. Do try to hurry up.

Request - Please, Tom, come here. Please put your pencils down. Suggestion and persuasion
- Let's start now. Let's not waste any more time.

It can be concluded that modal verbs and the imperative mood are the most commonly used means of expressing speech etiquette. This can be justified by the fact that the instructions of the teacher must be clear and precise, setting the students to perform certain actions.

There is always a didactic orientation in the teacher's speech, i.e. Simultaneously with the transfer of information, learning tasks are solved. This puts forward special requirements for the selection, methods of organizing and presenting information, for the forms of pedagogical speech, in particular for filling speech with etiquette formulas characteristic of the English-speaking society.

The oral speech of the teacher serves as a model that is perceived by the student and by which he learns to build his speech. At the same time, it should be remembered that for the student, the speech of the teacher is often the only example of the literary norm and the correct presentation of foreign language speech. Because of this, special attention should be paid to the form of pedagogical speech, its normative nature and proximity to the speech of modern native speakers.

The aim of the present study was to determine whether an association exists between the duration of menopause and the age of menopause onset, and the differences in bone mineral density (BMD) in postmenopausal women. ¹

A special place in the work of Utkir Khashimov is occupied by the novel "Between Two Doors". The writer is concerned not only with the pressing social issues of today, but with eternal moral problems. In particular, by calling "Between Two Doors", the writer means the path of person, which he walked from birth to death. ²

The article considers the role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism in Uzbekistan. In the conditions of innovative development of the economy, sustainable development of tourism occurs as a result of economic integration and the systematic improvement of international relations. With the innovative development of the economy, the role and prestige of tourism in the national economy is growing. Tourism is one of the most profitable sectors of the economy. ³

Today richness of Uzbek terminology is mainly due to the use of other languages and word formation is giving. The main factor that determines the stability of a particular terminological system in a particular field is its regularity. ⁴

The communicative method as the ultimate goal of learning involves the formation of communicative competence, which consists of linguistic, speech, subject, socio-cultural, educational and compensatory competencies. ⁵

¹ Najmutdinova, D. K., Nurmukhamedova, L. S., Alieva, D. A., Maksudova, D. S., & Nosirova, Z. A. (2016). Study of the effects of the age at menopause and duration of menopause on bone mineral density in postmenopausal women in Uzbekistan. *International Journal of Biomedicine*, 6(1), 38-40.

² Turaeva, K., & Zarinabonu, A. (2022). Interpretation Of Woman Image in Modern Uzbek Literature (Based on Utkir Khashimov's Book "Between Two Doors"). *Eurasian Research Bulletin*, 4, 42-44.

³ Abdullaeva, A. A., & Kizi, K. D. R. (2020). Role of the state in ensuring sustainable development of tourism. *European science*, (1 (50)).

⁴ Bakhtiyorovna, N. M., & Zoirovna, N. I. Terms and Terminology in the Uzbek and English Languages. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 173-176.

⁵ Абдуллаева, Л. С., Самадова, С. А., & Махмурова, М. (2014). Современные методы преподавания иностранных языков. *Коммуникативный метод. Наука. Мысль: электронный периодический журнал*, (6), 73-76.

The main purpose of teaching computer graphics in school in the article is to teach students the order and rules of computer-aided drawing of graphic information, such as drawings, diagrams and schemes, performed in the disciplines of drawing and engineering graphics.⁶

This article is devoted to the study of Somerset Maugham's short story "The Book Bag". It mainly focuses on the analysis of moral and immoral issues, emphasizing to the matter of incest and its fatal outcomes.⁷

The article considers the correlation of the real facts and imagination in "Tamburlaine the Great" by Christopher Marlowe.⁸

Synonyms are formed from the combination of the Greek words syn" together"+ onoma" name", which is an important means of increasing the effectiveness of speech, a clearer, more vivid, logical and diverse expression of thought.⁹

The nature of the semantic volume of the word, language corpus and creating Uzbek language corpus is under the analysis of this article. This issue of principle importance for semasiological research has been interpreted in different ways in linguistics.¹⁰

This article covers the main place of small business and business in today's market economy. Including scientifically analyzed the development of small business and business, and the legal basis, at this time financially support small business and business, the latter is amended and the rules for this branch of national legislation are added.¹¹

In the national economy, as in the economic systems of a number of foreign countries, the concept of public-private partnership (PPP) is being actively implemented.¹²

This article discusses the socio-philosophical importance of gender equality in today's increasingly globalized world. At the same time, in Uzbekistan, which is developing rapidly in all directions, the current issues of women's legal freedoms, protection of their legitimate interests, social relations of women in society and the development of society, social cohesion, family, traditions, It has been scientifically stated that culture, international and inter-civilizational relations, religion, labor and organization of public organizations are of great importance.¹³

Speech etiquette has national specifics - a teacher and a student receiving a pedagogical education must not only master the literary norm, but also carefully study the culture of the country of the language being studied, the specifics of speech etiquette, verbal etiquette formulas and clichés

⁶ Ruzimurodova, Z., & Mamatov, D. K. (2021). PECULIARITIES OF THE USE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING ENGINEERING GRAPHICS. *World Bulletin of Social Sciences*, 4(11), 136-140.

⁷ Pulatova, S. (2021). SUPERIORITY OF MORAL IDEAS AND FATAL RESULTS OF IMMORALITY IN THE SHORT STORY OF SOMERSET MAUGHAM "THE BOOK BAG". *Збірник наукових праць ЛОГОΣ*.

⁸ Temirovna, M. P. (2021). THE CORRELATION OF HISTORICAL TRUTH AND IMAGINATION IN CHRISTOPHER MARLOWE'S TRAGEDY "TAMBURLAINE THE GREAT". *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 2(12), 455-457.

⁹ Mirxanova, G. R. (2021). EMERGENCE AND STAGE OF DEVELOPMENT OF FIRST SYNONYM DICTIONARIES. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University*, 5(2), 96-105.

¹⁰ Bahodirovna, A. D. Semantic Labeling of Language Units. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 3(1), 177-179.

¹¹ Tolibjonovich, Madumarov T., and Gulomjonov O. R. Ogli. "Lombard Microcredit Organization Its Concept and Its Importance Today." *JournalNX*, vol. 6, no. 10, 2020, pp. 109-111.

¹² Madumarov Talatbek Tolibjonovich, & Gulomjonov Odiljon Rahimjon o'g'li. (2021). PREREQUISITES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A LEASING MECHANISM IN PUBLIC - PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6(SP), 5. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7MXR3>

¹³ Фуломжонов, О. Р. Ў. (2021). ЖАМИЯТ ТАРАҚҚИЁТИНИНГ ЯНГИ БОСҚИЧИДА ГЕНДЕР ТЕНГЛИКНИ ТАЪМИНЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОИЙ АҲАМИЯТИ. *Scientific progress*, 1(4).

characteristic of the language. Such activities in the future will significantly improve the speech of the teacher, which will accordingly have a positive effect on the educational process and provide students with the opportunity to hear formulas at each lesson and use them in their own speech.

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